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Research Paper

Scientific DSR Validation, Pharmacognostical, Biodiversity, Toxicological Research Studies of *Nyctanthes Arborescens* L.- Aerial Leaves Part and Their Pharmacological, Therapeutic Medicinal Values

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ABSTRACT

Botanical, Pharmacognostical, Biodiversity and Toxicological research studies of ASU herbal products remains a big challenging task on global levels. There needs to be more than the advance investigation research studies and screening parameters to validation, authenticate, identification and differentiate adulterants.. *Nyctanthes arborescens* L. is one of the herbs used to treat various health wellness and therapeutic illness of public mankind from since ancient time. This study aims to evaluate the Botanical, Pharmacognostical, Biodiversity and Toxicological research studies of the plant of NAT. The Botanical, Pharmacognostical, Biodiversity and Toxicological authenticate identification, quality control research studies of the plant of NAT powder were carried out using standard methods. The studies explored of quality, safety and toxicity effects of the tested drug samples were also investigated applied standard methods WHO/AOAC/AYUSH pharmacopeias. The Botanical, Pharmacognostical, Biodiversity, Toxicological QC. QA. Properties of NAT have shown that all the investigated parameters were within the permissible limits. The tested drug samples showed significant quality, safety and toxicity studies against certain pathogens organisms and promising anti-pathogenic activity. In the investigated studies of Botanical, Pharmacognostical, QC.

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Toxicological research findings revealed that the revalidated test drug was free from adulterations and toxic contaminations. This investigated herb research data confirmed to revalidated of drug developed standard Atlas, Pharmacovigilance and therapeutic medicinal values may treat that the drug is safe for internally use and cures in as Antiarthritis, Antistress, Anti-inflammatory, Antimicrobial, Antibacterial, Antifungal, Hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic activity, Antiviral activity, Antiulcer activity, Analgesic activity, Anticancer activities, Cytotoxic activities, Obstinate Sciatica disorder etc.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that herbal medicines are able to fulfill the health requirements of approximately 80% of the global population, particularly those residing in rural regions of developing nations. The quality assurance and quality control of herbal crude drugs and formulated products are important in justifying their acceptability in modern system of medicine. Hence it is required to conduct the advance research on drugs standardization and product validation to provide effective, curable and safe drugs to the needy mass suffering from various ailments.(1-2),(9-15),(19-20),(27) As per Hindu mythology, the Harsinghar/ Parijata tree is recognized as one of the five wish-granting trees associated with Devaloka.(6),(17) *N. arbor-tristis* is commonly referred to as “Night Jasmine or Harsinghar.” The genus name “Nycatanthes” is derived from the Greek phrases “Nykhta,”

meaning night, and “anther,” meaning flower. Within the botanical family of Oleaceae, Night Jasmine genus encompasses more than 600 species of little trees and vines.(6),(17) A species of plant known as *N. arbortristis* and these glabrous twining shrubs are commonly found in tropical Asia and warm temperate regions of Europe and Africa. Additionally, they are extensively cultivated in gardens within these areas.^{[6],[82]} The plant is widely recognized across the country for its aromatic white flowers. The plant is distributed over several regions, namely southern India, northern Pakistan, Thailand, Malaysia, and Indonesia. Its original habitat is the subtropical Himalayas of Nepal and India. (6),(82) The species is distributed over several regions in India, including the outer Himalayas, the Jammu and Kashmir region, East Assam, Bengal, Tripura, and the central region extending to the Godavari River in the southern part. The plant flourishes in soil that is reddish-black in color and has a pH level between 5.6 and 7.5. It is well-suited for dry and semi-arid conditions.^{[6],[8],[26]} At present, there is a desperate need for the development of quality parameters for herbal drugs and raw plant materials. The WHO has emphasized the need to ensure the quality of medicinal plant products by using any advanced controlled techniques. (118),(121)

Nomenclature:

Sanskrit:	Parijatha/ Sephalka, Rajanikasa	Marath:	Parijathak/ Khurasli/ Partaka
Hindi:	Harsingar / Siharu	Gujarathi:	Jayaparvati
English:	Night Jasmine/ Coral jasmine/ Weeping nycatanthes	Telugu:	Pagadamalle/ Shwetasurasa
Bengali:	Sephalka / Singhar	Oriya:	Gangasiuli
Malayalam:	Parijatakam/ Manpumaram	Kannada:	Parijatha.
Punjabi:	Kuri/Laduri	Tamil:	Pavalamalligai
Urdu:	Harsingar		

Taxonomical Classification:

Kingdom:	Plantae	Divisin:	Magnoliophyta
Class:	Magnoliopsida	Order:	Lamiales
Family:	Oleaceae	Genus:	Nyctanthes
Species:	Arbortristis	Binomial Name:	<i>Nyctanthes arbortristis</i> Linn.

Bio diversity of herbaceous medicinal plant

***Nyctanthes arbortristis* L.:**

Name of plant	Worldwide Biodiversity and introduced from native regions	References
<i>Nyctanthes arbortristis</i> L.	Commonly found in tropical Asia and warm temperate regions of Europe and Africa, distributed over several regions, namely southern India, northern Pakistan, Thailand, Malaysia, and Indonesia. distributed over several regions in India, including the outer Himalayas, the Jammu and Kashmir region, Andhra Pradesh, East Assam, Bengal, Tripura, Orissa, Burma, Central India like Chhatanagpur, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh and southwards to Godavari and the central region extending to the Godavari River in the southern part and Asian region of Nepal and Sri Lanka.	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> , 2024(6); Panda <i>et al.</i> , 2024(8); Rawat <i>et al.</i> , 2021(26); Acharya, 2011 (82); Sasmal <i>et al.</i> ,2007 (95); Kirtikar and Basu, 2000 (117); Anonymous, Wealth of India,1997 (118) ; Varier,1995(124); Kiew and Bass, 1984 (135) ; Nadkarni,1982 (136)

NAT Investigated herbasious medicinal plant Whole plant parts Dried Stem barks, Leaves, Flower, Fruits with seeds parts , Dried Seeds and their investigated

studies Graphical Illustration, investigated plant Confirmation and identification by Herbarium sheets shown in Fig.-1, Fig.-2, Fig.-3, and Fig.-4 respectively.

Fig.-1, Graphical Illustration

Fig.-2, Botanical authentication of *N. arbortristis* by Authentic Specimen Herbarium Sheet basis.

Fig.-3, Dried Steam Bark, Leaves, Flowers part of *N. arbortristis*

Fig.-4, Fresh and Dried Seeds part of *N. arbortristis*

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Drug Collection and authentication, plant collection source: (1-2),(9-13),(19-20),(24),(41),(104-106),(116),(118),(126-127)

The raw drugs samples were procured and collected of the plant parts of NAT from the Central North - West region, Herbal Garden, PCIM&H Campus, Pocket-II, Scientific Block, Kamla Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad UP. India, South - North Region, RRIUM, Herbal Garden, Tamil Nadu State, India and North western Himalayas - Region, Shivalik Nagar, L-Block, Haridwar, Uttarakhand State, India and investigated plant parts of NAT samples authenticated and confirmed by Botany and Pharmacognosy Laboratory Section, Researcher Scientific Staff of Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine,

Royapuram, TN. State, Drug Standardization Research Institute, Botany Section, Ghaziabad, UP. and re-authenticated and reconfirmed by PCIM&H, Botany Department, Ghaziabad UP. India by the Authenticated confirmation of Herbariums Specimen Sheet basis. Researcher staffs using pharmacognostical standard methods after proper authentication, plant parts of NAT samples were washed thoroughly with clean water and dried under a gentle steam of air in the laboratory till no loss in weight temperature 30°C and powdered in an electric grinder.

Botanical and Pharmacognostical Studies: (1-2),(9-13),(19-20),(24),(116-117),(126-127) The dried Aerial part of NAT subjected to macroscopic studies as per approved format of API/UPI,AYUSH India standard methods and

evaluated systematically. Thin transverse section were taken from seeds samples stained with safranin and mounted in glycerin by following the micro technique methods. Microphotography was performed for the drug.(13),(104),(126) (127),(131) Quantitative Microscopy: The cleared materials were washed thoroughly and stained with safranin for quantitative microscopic studies. Maceration Study: Shade dried and coarsely powdered plant was treated with Jeffrey's reagent for a few hours. The action of the macerating fluid was stopped before the complete separation of all cells. Then the macerated tissue was carefully washed in distilled water to remove as much of the acid as possible and then transferred to 50% alcohol for study. Slides were made by placing

small quantities of cells in water on a slide. The excess water was evaporated, mounted in glycerin and observed through microscope.

Toxicological investigation study: (1-2),(9-15),(19-20),(22-23),(24),(104-106),(118),(121), (126-128),(131),(134) Standard Methods applied for detection and investigation of Toxicology study parameters, WHO/AOAC/AYUSH. Pharmacopeial permissible standard Limits basis, All investigated and tested samples of NAT have been carried out as per WHO/AOAC/AYUSH-API/UI Standard methods. Botanical, Pharmacognostical powder microscopical analysis, authentication and identification of fresh and dried Aerial parts NAT.:

**Fig.-5, *Nyctanthes arbortritis* Linn.
Aerial portion Microscopy**

Fig.-6, Powder Microscopy

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Macroscopic investigation: Investigated drug NAT occurred in pieces of varying thickness ranging from 0.4 to 0.6cm diameter and upto 7cm length; young stems green with smooth surfaces and swelling at nodes, older ones show a light brown; leaves simple, petiolate, petiole very small upto 0.7cm; lamina ovate with acute leaf tip, 3 to 12cm in length and 1.5 to 8cm in breadth, margin entire to slightly serrated, venation unicostate reticulate with pinnate incision; leaves dorsiventral, upper surface deep green in colour, slightly rough, hairs or trichomes very fine but firm (hirsute), lower surface light green in colour, smooth and soft; odour herbaceous, taste bitter and slightly astringent.

Microscopic investigation: Investigated drug NAT occurred in Aerial stem part : T.S. of stem shown anomalous secondary structure; circular in

outline with quadrangular ridges; presence of cortical vascular bundles apart from normal vascular bundle; epidermis consisting of single layer of thick walled parenchyma cells covered with cuticle; trichomes numerous, long thick walled cells with tapering ends, cortex consisting of few layers of collenchyma, chlorenchyma and parenchyma cells; pericycle consisting of patches of few sclerenchyma fibres; normal vascular bundles ring shaped occur in the central region with xylem elements towards the centre and phloem toward outside; four inversely oriented cortical vascular bundles present at four ridges with xylem towards outside and phloem towards inside; the vascular bundles collateral and open; pith present in the centre. Petiole: T.S. of petiole shown prominent notch towards the middle of upper peripheral zone; epidermis consisting of single layer of thick walled parenchyma cells

covered with cuticle; trichomes numerous long thick walled tapering cell; cortex consisting of few layers of collenchyma, chlorenchyma and parenchyma cells; vascular bundles 3 to 7 in number, bigger vascular bundles in the centre, where as lateral bundles comparatively smaller in size; each bundle consists of xylem towards the upper side and phloem towards the lower side of the bundle; a few sclerenchyma fibres present on the lower side of the vascular bundle. Leaf through Midrib: T. S. of leaf through midrib shows epidermis consisting of single layer of thick walled parenchyma cells with cuticle, numerous unicellular trichomes present on both the upper and lower side; cortex consisting of few layers of collenchyma, chlorenchyma and parenchyma cells; vascular bundle sickle shaped in the centre with xylem towards the upper side and phloem towards the lower side of the bundle; a few sclerenchyma fibres on the lower side of the vascular bundle. Lamina: T.S. of lamina shown dorsiventral; epidermis consisting of single layer of thick walled parenchyma cells with cuticle; trichomes of variable sizes present on both the upper and lower epidermis; palisade parenchyma consisting of two layers of elongated parenchyma cells on the upper side followed by 8 to 9 layers of spongy parenchyma on the lower side; numerous scattered stomata present on the lower epidermis; epidermal cells in surface view consisting of polygonal parenchyma cells with angular walls; anisocytic stomata present only in the lower epidermis; stomatal number of the lower epidermis 50 to 55/sq mm and stomatal index of the lower epidermis 40 to 42/sq mm; palisade ratio 9 to 11 and vein islet number 14 to 19. Shown in Fig.-5 respectively.

Powder Microscopy: Grayish brown; numerous elongated thick walled mostly unicellular trichomes upto 400 μ with gradually tapering tips; vessels with pitted thickening up to 45 μ ; thick walled elongated cells of fibers and tracheids up to

1300 μ and width upto 35 μ ; xylem parenchyma cells; upper epidermal cells in surface view with only trichomes; lower epidermal cells angular walls in surface view with anisocytic stomata and trichomes; palisade parenchyma cells in double layers and parenchyma cells in surface view. Shown in Fig.-6 respectively.

Ethno-medicinal uses and Biodiversity of investigated plant NAT:

(4),(6),(8),(18),(26),(82),(95),(117),(121),(122),(133-134)

The investigated herbaceous medicinal plant NAT was worldwide, ethno-medicinal uses and biodiversity occurred and found in tropical Asia and warm temperate regions of Europe and Africa, distributed over several regions, namely southern India, northern Pakistan, Thailand, Malaysia, and Indonesia. distributed over several regions in India, including the outer Himalayas, the Jammu and Kashmir region, Andhra Pradesh, East Assam, Bengal, Tripura, Orissa, Burma, Central India like Chhatanagpur, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh and southwards to Godavari and the central region extending to the Godavari River in the southern part and Asian region of Nepal and Sri Lanka uses by these Tribal's population's which have lived in these forest region from since ancient time that was found in the study plant used by Tribal's population's very broad level's, already gained of knowledge, well aware and well known upon practically therapeutic uses of study plant of NAT and well aware about their medicinal efficacy and medicinal values, wealthiest aspects and curable potent properties as Anti-inflammatory, Anti-helminthic, Antibilious, Antibacterial, Antifungal activities and Analgesic activity, Cold, Joint and Sciatica pain potential, illness, disorder's for curable of our health and these shown have beneficial medicinal curing potential developed of NAT from since ancient time. The study plant NAT had occurred ethno botanically, climatically and biodiversity appeared world wide occurrences

presence in rich form of investigated herbaceous medicinal plant. Investigated medicinal plant NAT has been present and confirmed bioactive phytochemical constituents having numerous secondary metabolites, detail shown in Table-1 respectively.

Toxicological investigated study : (1-2),(9-15),(19-20),(22-23),(24),(28-29),(41),(46),(104-1061),(118),(131) Studies Medicinal plant NAT has been using and applied of Advance sophisticated Instruments and operating parameters detections and investigations of Heavy Metals - Pb, As, Cd, Hg in ppm. levels by Thermo Fisher M Series, 650902 V1.27 model Atomic Absorption Spectrometer with Graphite Furnace (AAS-GF), Aflatoxins - B1,B2 and G1,G2 in ppm. levels were estimated by Kobra cell techniques using CAMAG or Anchrom HPTLC instrument, Revolution Front (Rf) values detect in cm. range, Detector - UV-Visible detector, Detector temperature :25°C, Sample injector volume range - 5.0µl to 20µl range, Pesticide residues in mg/kg and bio active components were analyzed using Gas Chromatography Mass Spectra (GC-MS) (Instrument- Thermo Scientific, Model TSQ9000), detector-mass selective detector or Triple Quadrupole mass analyzer detector, column specification-TG-5MS / Run time- usually for the investigated compounds vary according to the method of GC and temperature programming whereas roughly all the all the relevant bio active phyto-chemical constituents usually appear in an around 0-50 minutes in the GC column i.e. the Retention time, Run time usually varies with the method and GC temperature program. Mass value range - 0.0 to 650amu, Sample injector volume

range - 1.0 µl to 5.0 µl. Microbial Load contamination - TBC/TFC detect in cfu/gm. *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhai* Spp. *Staphylococcus aurous* author pathogenic, detection and estimation in Heavy Metals-Pb, Hg, Cd and As, Aflatoxins- B1,B2 and G1, G2 and Pesticide Residues - Organo chlorine, pesticides, Organo phosphorus pesticides, Pyrethroids etc, in ppm levels concentrations. NAT. having investigated bioactive phytochemical constituents with immense, remarkable therapeutic medicinal potential values, pharmacological action properties, shown in Table-1 respectively, and Toxicologically investigated of collected samples of various 3 regions from India, arial plant part 3 samples of NAT. medicinal plant shown, toxicological QC., QA. research data's. Toxicology investigated research parameters revealed results were shown with in prescribed WHO/AYUSH Pharmacopeial permissible standard Limits in as Microbial Load contaminations - TBC/TFC detect in cfu/gm. *Escherichia coli* , *Salmonella typhai* Spp. *Staphylococcus aurous* author pathogenic, detection and in Heavy Metals-Pb, Hg, Cd and As, Aflatoxins B1,B2 and G1,G2 and Pesticide Residues - Organo chlorine, pesticides, Organo phosphorus pesticides, Pyrethroids etc. in ppm. Level's and potentially toxic elements detections in ppb. levels. Resulted the all investigated Toxicology research parameters found in the study medicinal plant investigated 3 samples shown complies and not found of any hazardous or highly toxic contamination in the investigated drug samples, It had fit for internal used. Investigated results shown in Table's - 4,5,6 and 7 respectively.

Table -1, Investigated Major Active- Phyto-chemical Constituents in NAT:

Plant	Part Used	Major Active- Phytochemical Constituents	References
<i>Nyctanthes arbortristis</i> Linn. (Night Jasmine)	Leaves	Hexadecanoic acid (26.4%), phytol (13.6%), Hexenyl benzoate (11%), Linalool (11.3%), Octadecanoic acid (6.2%), Methyl salicylate (5.6%), n-Dodecanol (5.5%), Alpha-Terpineol (4.7%), and Geraniol (3.7%), D-mannitol, β -sitosterole, astragaline, nicotiflorin, oleanolic acid, nyctanthic acid, tannic acid, ascorbic acid, methyl salicylate, carotene, friedeline, lupeol, mannitol, glucose and fructose, iridoid glycosides, Flavanol glycosides, benzoic acid, derivative of kaempferol, carotene.	Swain <i>et al.</i> ,2024(4) ;Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024(6) ; Kushwah <i>et al.</i> , 2023 (18) ; Satyal <i>et al.</i> , 2012(80) ; Hukkeri , <i>et al.</i> , 2006(107) .
	Stem Barks	Hexadecanoic acid (34.3%), Alpha-Eudesmol (8.7%), Beta-Eudesmol (17.1%), Elemol (5.8%), Cryptomeridiol (4.8%), Octadecanoic acid (3.9%), n-Dodecanol (6.8%), Methyl palmitate (1.8%), Methyl stearate (1.4%), and 1,8-Cineole (1.3%),Glycoside-naringenin-4''-0- β -glucapyranosyl- α -xylo pyranoside and β -sitosterol, Glycosides and alkaloids.	Swain <i>et al.</i> ,2024(4) ;Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> , 2024 (6) ;Kushwah <i>et al.</i> , 2023 (18) ; Satyal <i>et al.</i> , 2012 (80) ;Vats <i>et al.</i> , 2009 (90) ; Girach <i>et al.</i> , 1994 (124)
	Flowers	1-octanol (74.81%), 2-hexadecen-1-ol, 3,7,11,15-tetra (6.8%), Bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (5.88%), 2,4-cycloheptadiene-1-one, 2,6,6-trimethyl (4.23%), Hexadecanoic acid methyl ester (2.07%), and Benzoic acid (1.21%), Phytol (32.2%), Methyl palmitate (14.7%), <i>cis</i> -9-Tricosene (3.6%), Geranylgeraniol (2.7%), n-Nonadecene (2.2%), Phytone (1.4%), Methyl stearate (1.1%), n-Benzyl salicylate (1.1%), and Heptacosane (0.8%), Essential oil, Nyctanthin, D-mannitol, Tannin and Glucose, Carotenoid, glycosides viz β -monogentiobioside ester of α -crocetin (or crocin-3), β monogentiobioside- β -D monoglucoside ester of α -crocetin, β -digentiobioside ester of α -crocetin. (or crocin-1), 4- hydroxy hexahydrobenzofuran-7-one.	Swain <i>et al.</i> ,2024(4) ;Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024(6) ; Kushwah <i>et al.</i> , 2023 [18] ; Karthick <i>et al.</i> , 2019(33) ; Sriwardena <i>et al.</i> , 2014(52) ; Thangavelu <i>et al.</i> , 2010 (83)
	Seeds	Arbortristoside A&B, Pale Yellow Brown Oil (15%), Glycerides of linoleic oleic, Lignoceric, Stearic, Palmitic and Myristic acids, Nyctanthic acid, Nyctoside A, β -sitosterol, 3-4 secotriterpene acid and A water soluble polysaccharide composed of D-glucose and D-mannos	Swain <i>et al.</i> ,2024(4) ;Kushwah <i>et al.</i> , 2023 (18) ; Adebajo <i>et al.</i> ,2007(96)

	Roots	β -Sitosterol and Oleanolic acid	Swain <i>et al.</i> ,2024(4) ;Jain <i>et al.</i> ,2011(77)
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Pharmacological and Therapeutics medicinal potent values of NAT:

Nyctanthes arbortristis, (NAT) also known as Harsinghar / Parijata / coral jasmine/night jasmine, is a plant that has gained attention for its therapeutic properties and medicinal applications. NAT various plant parts has been investigated in Leaves, Flowers, Stem Bark, Seeds, Fruits *In-vitro*, *In-vivo* pharmacological studies and confirmation, explored their remarkable therapeutic and medicinal potential.(3),(6),(30) Respectively Shown in Table -2. Anticancer

activities has been investigated in Leaves, Flower's, Dried Fruit's, Fruits, leaves, and Stem barks parts of NAT.(4-5),(6),(18),(31) Tumour necrosis factor Depleting activity has been investigated in Leave's part of NAT.(30) Cytotoxic activities has been investigated in Flower's part of NAT. (6),(30),(111),(115) Antiproliferative, Anticancer activities in Flower's part of NAT. (4) and Cytotoxic activities has been investigated in Leaves and Stem, Stem, leaves, and Fruits parts of NAT. (30) Respectively Shown in Table -3.

Table -2, Investigated Pharmacological Activities in In-vitro & In-vivo NAT studies:

Investigated Plant parts	Used in Studies Extracts	Study plan	Pharmacological Activities	References
Leaves	Ethanollic extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antibacterial activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Gahtori <i>et al.</i> , 2024 ^[7]
Leaves	Aqueous extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antibacterial activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Rani <i>et al.</i> , 2023 ^[17]
Leaves	Ethanollic, Methanollic, Petroleum ether, and Aqueous extracts	<i>In vitro</i>	Antibacterial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Vyas <i>et al.</i> ,2013 ^[65]
Leaves	Ethanollic extract	<i>In vitro</i>	Antibacterial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Show <i>et al.</i> ,2014 ^[54]
Leaves	Ethyl acetate extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-fungal activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6]
Leaves	Ethanollic extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Gahtori <i>et al.</i> , 2024 ^[7]
Leaves	Aqueous extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Rani <i>et al.</i> , 2023 ^[17]
Leaves	Petroleum ether extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antimicrobial activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Pandey <i>et al.</i> ,2016 ^[14]
Leaves	Betulinic acid	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Karan <i>et al.</i> ,2019 ^[32]
Leaves	β -sitosterol isolated from petroleum ether extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Analgesic activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Nirmal <i>et al.</i> ,2012 ^[74]

Leaves	Petroleum ether extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-inflammatory activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Nirmal <i>et al.</i> ,2012 ^[74]
Leaves	Ethanollic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Mousum <i>et al.</i> ,2018 ^[35]
Leaves	Petroleum ether extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Hepatoprotective activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Chaudhary <i>et al.</i> ,2018 ^[36]
Leaves	Methanol extract and Chloroform extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Larvicidal activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Pandey <i>et al.</i> ,2016 ^[42]
Leaves	Ethanollic Extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antiviral activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Kannan <i>et al.</i> ,2007 ^[99]
Leaves	Aqueous Extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antiviral activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Kannan <i>et al.</i> ,2010 ^[99]
Leaves	Water-soluble fraction	<i>In-vivo</i>	Immunostimulatory activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Devasree <i>et al.</i> ,2014 ^[53]
Leaves	β -sitosterol isolated from petroleum ether extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Immunostimulatory activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Nirmal <i>et al.</i> ,2012 ^[74]
Leaves	95 % ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-inflammatory activity and Analgesic activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Saxena <i>et al.</i> ,1987 ^[129]
Leaves	90% ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-inflammatory activity and Analgesic activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Pattanayak <i>et al.</i> ,2013 ^[61]
Leaves	90% ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Cognitive impairment	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Phanindhra <i>et al.</i> ,2015 ^[47]
Leaves	Water-soluble extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Ulcerogenic activity and Antipyretic	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Saxena <i>et al.</i> ,1987 ^[129]
Leaves	Aqueous extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antipyretic	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Bhatia <i>et al.</i> ,2001 ^[113]
Leaves	95% Ethanolic, 50% hydro-alcoholic	<i>In-vivo</i>	Immuno-modulator/ Immunorestorative activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Agrawal <i>et al.</i> ,2013 ^[62]
Leaves	95% ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antiarthritic activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Goyal <i>et al.</i> ,2013 ^[64]
Leaves	Ethyl acetate extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antiarthritic activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; ;

				Uroos et al.,2017 ^[38]
Leaves	Methanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Hepato-protective activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Vishwanathan et al.,2010 ^[89]
Leaves	Methanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Hepato-protective activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Mahida et al.,2007 ^[102]
Leaves	Ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Hepato-protective activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Sathiya et al.,2008 ^[94]
Leaves	50% Ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antidiabetic activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Husain et al.,2010 ^[84]
Leaves	Ursolic acid	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antifilarial activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Saini et al.,2014 ^[56]
Leaves	Herbal Formulation preparation (250mg powder/5 ml suspension)	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antifilarial activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Ghiware et al.,2007 ^[98]
Leaves	Fresh paste of leaves	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antifilarial activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Karnik et al.,2008 ^[93]
Leaves	Ethanolic extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antifilarial activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Kumari et al.,2012a ^[78]
Leaves	Fresh preparation of leaves paste	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antimalarial activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Godse et al.,2016 ^[45]
Leaves	Methanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Wound healing activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Sopi et al.,2013 ^[58]
Leaves	Ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Hypoglycemic activity	Kaliyaperumal et al.,2024 ^[6] ; Mobyia et al.,2023 ^[16]
Leaves	Aqueous extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Dasgupta et al.,2007 ^[97]
Leaves, Stem	Ethanolic extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Immuno-modulator/ Immunorestorative activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Thomas et al.,2013 ^[63]
Flowers	Dry flower aqueous extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Vankar et al.,2008 ^[92]
Flowers	Ethanolic, Ethyl acetate, and Aqueous extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	Kaliyaperumal et al.,2024 ^[6] ; Mishra et al.,2016 ^[43]
Flowers	Ethanolic extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antibacterial activity	Kaliyaperumal et al.,2024 ^[6] ; Gahtori et al., 2024 ^[7]
Flowers	Ethanolic extract	<i>In vitro</i>	Antibacterial activity	Parekh et al.,2020 ^[30] ; Srinivasan et al.,2011 ^[81]

Flowers	Alcoholic extract utilized for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles	<i>In vitro</i>	Antibacterial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Gogoi <i>et al.</i> ,2015 ^[18]
Flowers	Water-soluble fraction of 70% ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antiarthritic activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Deshmukh <i>et al.</i> ,2007 ^[101]
Flowers	Aqueous extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-fungal activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 [6] ; Jamdagni <i>et al.</i> ,2018 ^[37]
Flowers	Crude aqueous extracts -Methanol fraction Hexane fraction	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-proliferative activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Heendeniya <i>et al.</i> , 2020 ^[31]
Flowers	Aqueous extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Hypoglycemic and Hypolipidemic activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Rangika <i>et al.</i> ,2015 ^[49]
Flowers	Aqueous extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Hepato-protective activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Wagh <i>et al.</i> ,2010 ^[85]
Flowers	Petroleum ether, Chloroform, and Ethyl acetate extracts	<i>In vitro</i>	Hepato-protective activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Khatune <i>et al.</i> , 2001 ^[114]
Flowers	Chloroform extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Larvicidal activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Sah <i>et al.</i> ,2012 ^[75]
Flowers	Ethanolic extracts, Rengyolone 1 and its acetate derivative	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antifilarial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Tuntiwachwuttikul <i>et al.</i> , 2003 ^[110]
Flowers	Zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized using aqueous extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-fungal activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Jamdagni <i>et al.</i> ,2018 ^[37]
Flowers	Aqueous extracts	<i>In-vivo</i>	Hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Rangika <i>et al.</i> ,2015 ^[49]
Stem Bark	Ethanol extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-diabetic activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Suresh <i>et al.</i> ,2010 ^[86]
Stem Bark	Methanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-inflammatory activity and Analgesic activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Kakoti <i>et al.</i> ,2013 ^[60]
Stem Bark	Ethyl acetate extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-arthritis activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Puri <i>et al.</i> ,1994 ^[125]

Stem Bark	Petroleum ether, Chloroform, and Ethanol extracts	<i>In-vivo</i>	Hepato-protective activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Manisha <i>et al.</i> ,2009 ^[91]
Stem Bark	Ethanol extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antibacterial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Suresh <i>et al.</i> ,2010 ^[86]
Stem Bark	Aqueous/Methanolic extract		Antioxidant activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Thakur <i>et al.</i> ,2017 ^[40]
Seed-kernel	Iridoid glucosides	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antimalarial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Shukla <i>et al.</i> ,2012 ^[76]
Seeds	n-Butanol fraction of 50% ethanolic extract, Arbotristoside-A, and Arbotristoside C	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antiviral activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Gupta <i>et al.</i> ,2005 ^[108]
Seeds	Arbotristoside-A (AT) and 7- <i>O</i> -trans-cinnamoyl-6-hydroxyloganin (6-HL) ethanolic extract	<i>In-vitro</i> & <i>In-vivo</i>	Antiulcer activity	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Mishra <i>et al.</i> ,2013 ^[59]
Seeds	Methanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Immunostimulatory activity	Kirubakaran <i>et al.</i> ,2016 ^[6] ; Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30]
Seeds	Chloroform extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Immuno-modulator/ Immunorestorative activity	Kirubakaran <i>et al.</i> ,2010 ^[6] ; Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30]
Seeds	Arbotristoside-A and 7- <i>O</i> -trans-cinnamoyl6 β -hydroxyloganin	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-ulcerogenic activity/ Ulcer healing property	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Mishra <i>et al.</i> ,2013 ^[59]
Fruits	Water-soluble fraction of 50% ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antistress activity, Anti-oxidant activity, Antibacterial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ;Tripathi <i>et al.</i> ,2013 ^[67]
Fruits	Methanolic extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Kumari <i>et al.</i> ,2012b ^[73]
Fruits	Petroleum ether and Methanolic extracts	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antibacterial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Shinde <i>et al.</i> ,2014 ^[55]
Leaves and Fruits	99% ethanolic extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antifilarial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Simonsen <i>et al.</i> ,2001 ^[112]

Fruits, Seeds, and Leaves	Water-soluble ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Immuno-modulator/ Immunorestorative activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Rathore <i>et al.</i> ,2007 ^[100]
Leaves and Stem Bark	Hydro-alcoholic extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antibacterial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Satyal <i>et al.</i> ,2011 ^[80]
Leaves, Flower, Fruits, and Seeds	Ethyl acetate and Chloroform extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Hepato-protective activity and Antibacterial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Priya <i>et al.</i> ,2007 ^[103]
Flowers, leaves and Seeds	50% ethanolic extract of seeds, flowers and leaves, aqueous fractions	<i>In-vivo</i>	Immuno-stimulant activity	Rajput <i>et al.</i>,2024^[3] ; Puri <i>et al.</i> ,1994 ^[125]
Leaves, Seed , Flower, Stem, and Root	50% ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antipyretic	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Khan <i>et al.</i> ,1995 ^[123]
Whole plant	80% methanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Immunostimulatory activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Bhalerao <i>et al.</i> , 2011 ^[78]
Whole plant material	Aqueous, Ethanol, Benzene, Petroleum ether, and Chloroform extracts	<i>In vitro</i>	Antibacterial activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Aggarwal <i>et al.</i> ,2013 ^[66]
Root barks	Aqueous, Ethanolic, Petroleum ether, and Chloroform extracts	<i>In vitro</i>	Hepato-protective activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Verma <i>et al.</i> ,2011 ^[78]

Table -3, Anticancer and Antitumor, Cytotoxic activity of flowers aqueous extract of NAT:

Investigated Plant parts	Used in Studies Extracts	Study plan	Pharmacological Activities	References
Leaves	Ethanolic extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Tumour necrosis factor Depleting activity	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Paul <i>et al.</i> ,1997 ^[120]
Leaves	Methanolic extract	<i>In-vitro</i> , A-549 cancer cell line	Anticancer activities	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Kumari <i>et al.</i> ,2017 ^[39]
Flowers	Crude aqueous extracts- Chloroform fraction, Ethyl acetate fraction, Hexane fraction	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anticancer activities	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[6] ; Heendeniya <i>et al.</i> , 2020 ^[31]

Flowers	Ethyl acetate, Ethanolic and aqueous extracts	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anticancer activities	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Khanapur <i>et al.</i> ,2014 ^[57]
Dried fruit	Methanol extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anticancer activities	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> , 2024 ^[6] ; Gulshan <i>et al.</i> ,2015 ^[50]
Fruits, leaves, and Stem barks	Methanol extract	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anticancer (human breast cancer) activities	Kushwah <i>et al.</i> ,2023 ^[18] ; Khatu <i>et al.</i> ,2001 ^[114]
Flowers	Flower extracts synthesized ZnO nanoparticle	<i>In vitro</i>	Anticancer activities	Swain <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[4] ; Chabattula <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[5]
Flowers	Petroleum ether, Chloroform, and Ethyl acetate extracts	<i>In vitro</i>	Cytotoxic activities	Kaliyaperumal <i>et al.</i> , 2024 ^[6] ; Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Khatune <i>et al.</i> ,2001 ^[115]
Flowers	Ethyl acetate and ethanol extracts	<i>In-vivo</i>	Antiproliferative, Anticancer activities	Swain <i>et al.</i> ,2024 ^[4] ; Khanapur <i>et al.</i> ,2014 ^[57] ; Susan <i>et al.</i> ,1986 ^[132]
Flowers	Crude aqueous extracts	<i>In vitro</i>	Cytotoxic activities	Naznin <i>et al.</i> ,2001 ^[111]
Leaves and Stem	Successive extraction using hexane and ethanol	<i>In-vitro</i>	Cytotoxic activities	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Chidi <i>et al.</i> ,2015 ^[51]
Stem, leaves, and Fruits	Methanolic extract	<i>In-vitro</i>	Cytotoxic activities	Parekh <i>et al.</i> ,2020 ^[30] ; Kumari <i>et al.</i> ,2012b ^[73]

Table - 4: Analysis of Microbial load (By WHO/AOAC/AYUSH/API/UPI Std. Methods)

S. NO.	Parameter Analyzed	Results			WHO Limit
		NAT - 1	NAT - 2	NAT - 3	
1	Total Bacterial Count	580 cfu/gm	584 cfu/gm	584 cfu/gm	10 ⁵ cfu/gm
2	Total Fungal Count	630 cfu/gm	636 cfu/gm	632 cfu/gm	10 ³ cfu/gm
3	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
4	<i>Salmonella typhai Spp.</i>	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
5	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent

Table - 5: Estimation of Heavy Metals (By AAS-GF)

S. NO.	Parameter Analyzed	Results			WHO Limit
		NAT - 1	NAT - 2	NAT - 3	
1	Lead	3.02ppm	3.03ppm	3.04ppm	10ppm
2	Cadmium	0.04ppb	0.03ppb	0.04ppb	0.3ppm
3	Mercury	N/D	N/D	N/D	1.0ppm
4	Arsenic	0.05 ppm	0.05 ppm	0.04 ppm	3.0ppm

Table - 6: Estimation of Aflatoxins (By HPTLC)

S. NO.	Parameter Analyzed	Results			WHO Limit
		NAT - 1	NAT - 2	NAT - 3	
1	Aflatoxin, B1	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.5ppm
2	Aflatoxin, B2	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.1ppm
3	Aflatoxin, G1	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.5ppm
4	Aflatoxin, G2	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.1ppm

Table - 7, Estimation of Pesticide Residues (By GC-MS):

S. NO.	Parameter Analyzed	Results			WHO Limit in ppm.
		NAT - 1	NAT - 2	NAT - 3	
1	DDT (all isomers, sum of ρ , ρ' -DDT, α , ρ' DDT, ρ , ρ' -DDE and ρ , ρ' -TDE (DDD expressed as DDT)	N/D	N/D	N/D	1.0
2	HCH (sum of all isomers)	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.3
3	Endosulphan (all isomers)	N/D	N/D	N/D	3.0
4	Azinphos-methyl	N/D	N/D	N/D	1.0
5	Alachlor	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.02
6	Aldrin (Aldrin and dieldrin combined expressed as dieldrin)	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.05
7	Chlordane (cis& tans)	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.05
8	Chlorfenvinphos	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.5
9	Heptachlor (sum of heptachlor and heptachlor epoxide expressed as heptachlor)	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.05
10	Endrin	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.05
11	Ethion	N/D	N/D	N/D	2.0
12	Chlorpyrifos	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.2
13	Chlorpyrifos-methyl	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.1
14	Parathion methyl	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.2
15	Malathion	N/D	N/D	N/D	1.0
16	Parathion	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.5
17	Diazinon	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.5

18	Dichlorvos	N/D	N/D	N/D	1.0
19	Methidathion	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.2
20	Phosalone	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.1
21	Fenvalerate	N/D	N/D	N/D	1.5
22	Cypermethrin (including other mixtures of constituent isomers sum of isomers)	N/D	N/D	N/D	1.0
23	Fenitrothion	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.5
24	Deltamethrin	N/D	N/D	N/D	0.5
25	Permethrin (sum of isomers)	N/D	N/D	N/D	1.0
26	Pyrimiphos methyl	N/D	N/D	N/D	4,0

N/D Where:=Not Detect

CONCLUSIONS:

The investigated and revalidated 3 samples of Aerial plant part of NAT. drug were found to be of very good quality and devoid of any impurities or free from any hazardous, toxic contamination and adulterations according to the drug Authentications, identifications quality control revealed results data's basis. The ranges of all the Botanical, Pharmacognostical, Biodiversity, Toxicological by Standard methods of WHO/AOAC/AYUSH/API/ UPI, and AAS-GF, HPTLC,GC-MS investigated profiling research data's constants used for the quality analysis of the entire NAT aerial part 3 samples of the plant are normal. Numerous secondary metabolites have been detected and reconfirmed in the Botanical, Pharmacognostical, Biodiversity, Toxicological research by investigation, Analyzed and applied advance methods and sophisticated instruments techniques. The Toxicology investigation potential research data's have been shown that thus the aerial part's of the NAT fit for internal use as a drug supplement. The herbaceous medicinal plant NAT has been climatically very rich form in wild, worldwide biodiversity occurrence. As a result of its potent quality, safety and toxicity studies of properties, NAT may be treat and therapeutically used in various ASU traditional and alternative medicines preparations since ancient time. Investigated *In-vitro* ,*In-vivo* research reports data's confirmed therapeutic medicinal potent as a Anticancer activities,

Cytotoxic activities, Antiarthritis, Antistress, Antimicrobial, Antifungal, Antibacterial, Antioxidant, Anti-Inflammatory, Hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic activity, Antiviral activity, Antiulcer activity, Analgesic activity, Obstinate Sciatica disorder's from since ancient time. Investigated NAT - ASU drug can be incorporated and support to developed revalidation of novel drug development, investigation of novel bioactive marker constituents, compounds mechanism of actions, pharmacopoeial standard and atlas monographs, Pharmacovigilance aspects of NAT. However, Further studies are required to identify, isolate, and elucidate the structures of novel bioactive constituents present in NAT apply upon GC-MS, LC-MS, XRD, SEM-EDX advance sophisticated instruments techniques of these investigated drug scan still be carried out for purposes of advance research. that contribute to its health benefits. Besides, more evidence, especially through *In-vivo* and clinical trials, is necessary to determine the mechanisms involved in the bioactivities mentioned previously. Even though there are available preliminary data on the medicinal and nutritional values of NAT stem bark, root bark, flower, seeds parts information is still lacking, especially on other parts of the plant, such as the aerial leaves, stems bark. thus, studies on the these plant parts of NAT also be done to discover potential bioactive compounds that can be exploited for discover novel drug development and health advantages.

Limitations and Future Remarks of the Study:

The present studies data's of Botanical, Pharmacognostical, Biodiversity and Toxicological profiles shown the reconfirmation and presence of QC, QA, DSR, PV of arial part samples of NAT. In the future, investigated data may be used to Advance revalidation pharmacopoeial Drug Standardization Research, Pharmacopoeial atlas monographs profiling development, novel drug development, investigation of novel bioactive marker constituents, compounds mechanism of actions, Pharmacovigilance aspects and confirm these investigated resulted data's.

Ethical approval:

As the work is purely an In-vitro study, ethical clearance is not required.

Author's contributions:

Dr Pawan Kumar Sagar (Chemistry): Manuscript work designed, Carried out Instrumental, Chemistry part and Manuscript written and revised manuscript review. Dr. S. Sajwan, Dr. K.Venkatesan, Mrs. Jayanthi A, Dr. Mukesh Kumar and Dr. R M Singh: provide very helpful Support and Carried out Botanical, Pharmacognosy, taxonomy and biodiversity climatic occurrence, confirmation and authentication works designed and Research Material's Collection. Devi P M Sri, and Mr. S. Kashyap (Chemistry): carried out Toxicology, Microbiological and Analytical data analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest:

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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